

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE EFFICIENCY OF USING WIKI TECHNOLOGY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

Gaisina G.

*Master's student of the educational program "Foreign language teacher's training"
Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages*

Abstract

The most well-known example of wiki technology is Wikipedia, which is online software for building straightforward web pages that facilitate collaborative publishing. Wikis have the potential to be used in educational settings because of their features. These essential elements consist of a user-friendly interface for modifying the material, history tracking, authoring group size definition, and a non-linear editing structure. This research presents the findings of the perception of foreign language teachers on Wiki Technology in the classroom in order to investigate the function of the wiki in English language teaching. In order to understand the teachers' perspectives toward wiki technology in language instruction, this study used a quantitative research approach. English teachers who are proficient in digital literacy participated in this survey, which was done online. To have a better understanding of the instructors' opinions about wiki technology in language instruction, the questionnaire was designed as a Likert scale with four response possibilities. Based on the results of the questionnaire all research questions were covered. The study offers language instructors useful information about how to effectively use wiki technology in the classroom.

Keywords: wiki technology, wikis, digitalization, foreign language education, Wikipedia.

Introduction

The current global trend will undoubtedly lead to the fusion of cultures of different nationalities and close cooperation between countries. Relations between representatives of other nations and cultures, which formerly appeared unachievable, are now an essential aspect of life, even in education. The primary objective of the current educational system is also evolving. In this field, digitalization is also pervasive. As a result, these elements need to be looked at in greater detail. Wiki technologies are particularly important because they surely help to construct instructional activities.

The growth of Wikipedia, the most systematic information repository on the Internet, has made it possible for enormous projects for the gathering, sharing, and updating of knowledge to be built on wiki technology. It goes without saying that there is a lot of potential for improvement in the quality of many Wikipedia entries. Wikipedia is not a complete instructional website on its own. Wiki technology provides a ton of learning potential, as is readily seen from Wikipedia's social qualities and range of activities. Wiki technology can be used effectively and have a "wiki effect" on learning if its social, technological, and pedagogic aspects and functions are understood.

In this article, we would like to focus on the use of wiki technology in foreign language classes. With the help of the Wiki technology, anyone on the world may easily create, browse, modify, and publish hypertext pages in a variety of formats to one person or a group of people on the Internet.

Based on this, we will consider the possibilities and effectiveness of using the Wiki service for teaching a foreign language. Wiki technology is one of the categories of Web services that enables a distributed team to collaborate on the creation of a single document while making edits and additions to it. With the help of this definition, we can decide whether or not this tech-

nology is brand-new and capable of enabling entire cultural relations. This social service can also be used in pedagogical practice to present, expand, and annotate educational materials; jointly create virtual field trips for students and schoolchildren exploring local history, science, and the environment; jointly create creative works like fairy tales, poems, essays, and projects; jointly create teacher, student, and school encyclopedias and reference books; and jointly communicate professionally with other teachers to improve their professionalism. According to Sysoev (2008), Wiki is a tool for encouraging critical thinking and socialization in students. Working with Wiki enables students to apply the knowledge they have learned and developed during the English teaching process into practice, giving them a genuine experience of communicating in English. Using a wiki can be used for a variety of things, depending on the needs of the teacher and the students. Wiki, according to the evidence, ensures the success of autonomous work by giving each student the freedom to select the best method and rate for absorbing information. The experience of Western researchers has been summarized to the fullest extent by E. Tonkin (2005). He identifies three types of educational wikis:

- 1) individual wikis where the user saves and edits his thoughts;
- 2) laboratory wikis that allow storing records, as well as providing additional opportunities for peer review and editing by classmates;
- 3) wiki for group writing.

Having such opportunities, the wiki is not an actual technology in our educational field among teachers. Many teachers do not use this technology because it can be not so popular in our country, while it is actively used in other countries. Only Wikipedia is known in our nation, and for many people, that is the extent of their knowledge of it. As foreign language instructors, we would like to demonstrate that using Wiki technology in lessons may be a very effective way

by researching the issue of Wiki technology's usefulness in our nation. Therefore, it is desirable to questionnaire different respondents to justify the hypothesis that using Wiki technology in FLE by teachers is an effective way of teaching. Using a wiki can be used for a variety of things, depending on the needs of the teacher and the students. It is desirable to survey various respondents to support the hypothesis that the use of Wiki technology develops the ICC of students because evidence suggests Wiki ensures the effectiveness of independent work by giving each student the opportunity to select the best path and pace of assimilation of educational material. (Gaisina, 2022)

There has been a lot of discussion on the potential of Wikis in foreign language teaching and learning, but no thorough literature study has been done on the subject. This article aims to evaluate the existing employment of wikis in foreign language education in order to direct future research and language instruction. Specifically, this study addresses the following research questions:

1. What is the perception of foreign language teachers on Wiki Technology for in the classroom?

- Is it effective to use Wiki Technology for teachers in FLE?

- Has Wiki technology the ability to flatten traditional educational hierarchies, giving students greater autonomy and enticing them to exchange knowledge and educate one another?

- Can teachers use Wikis to establish students' social learning communities for knowledge creation and information sharing?

Literature review

Web 2.0 technology. The use of Web 2.0 tools in academia is growing, including blogs, podcasts, and wikis. Since the earliest use of the World Wide Web for teaching and learning, one of the most powerful elements has been the ability to engage learners in an interactive format (Hazari & Schnorr, 1999; Chandra & Lloyd, 2008). Technology skills must be incorporated by educators in the delivery of curricular content as technology continues to become more widely used for global communication and productivity. According to Schrand (2008), there are a number of advantages to using technology in the classroom for student motivation. According to Schrand, technology can encourage more engaged learning among students in the classroom while also catering to their varied intelligence and learning preferences. Wikis are one such Web 2.0 application that has demonstrated potential for social computing as a component of the Read/Write Web (also known as Web 2.0). The way users engage with web content has changed as a result of Web 2.0 tools.

Web 2.0 technology provides shared text, pictures, audio, and social network material. According to O'Reilly (2005), it is an example of the second generation of Internet services that are altering how people connect and collaborate online. Participants in Web 2.0 can design virtual online communities where people can interact and share ideas without being constrained by geography. Active user participation is one of the key characteristics of this new Web technology gener-

ation. According to Driscoll (2007), the majority of students not only understand how to use Web 2.0 teaching tools but also thrive in the environment when Web communication solutions are integrated into the classroom. Today's tech-savvy student generation actively participates in social networking and other online communications.

Wiki technology. Students can be empowered by technology tools (such as blogs and wikis) by having the opportunity to share their opinions. It can also aid students in developing their reading, writing, reflective, and collaborative learning abilities (Leight, 2008), which benefits students by having a positive psychological impact and aids organizations in utilizing a flexible environment that fosters collaboration and keeps up with technological innovation (Evans & Wolf, 2005). In schools, colleges, and universities, the use of wikis as a teaching tool has been investigated (Raman, Ryan & Olfman, 2005; Parker & Chao, 2007; Konieczny, 2007). Wikis' easy creation, modification, and tracking of collaborative material are one of their main draws. Any page or site can be readily expanded by users for discussion, assignment submission, and various team projects. Wiki technology makes it simple to work on a collaborative document, track work in progress, and determine the level of contribution from each member of a group (Andrew, 2008). Students are inspired to create work by using wikis in group situations, which they can later use in electronic portfolios and job interviews. Students gain abilities related to teamwork and idea sharing when using technological tools because the majority of firm's employ groupware software that enables collaboration comparable to Wikis.

Students can use wikis to establish social learning communities for knowledge creation and information sharing (Ruth & Houghton 2009). Chandra and Chalmers (2010) discussed how students utilized a wiki as a "social learning tool" to enable them to finish a group project together in research looking at the usage of wikis in a design and technology course.

Although some believe that students do not view this as the primary purpose of the technology (Hemmi et al. 2009; Kear et al. 2010), students may use a wiki as a forum for social interaction in addition to learning (Schwartz et al. 2004, Kear et al. 2010). Wikis and other social networking tools, according to some authors, give students in the "digital generation" the "architecture of participation." (Wheeler et al. 2008).

One of the tough challenges for all researchers in this domain is whether Wiki technology is a good fit for the constructivist learning philosophy, according to which students' creation of knowledge on wikis parallels their own internal knowledge production (Cole 2009; Te'tard et al. 2009). Godwin-Jones writes in his analysis of Web 2.0 technology that "The purpose of wiki sites is to become a shared repository of knowledge..." (Godwin-Jones 2003). Many authors have referred to this aspect of wiki technology. Wiki technology enables users to create a shared resource together by allowing multiple users to edit the content at different times while storing information in between edits (Holmes et al. 2001). According to West and West wikis can be used to "build an archive of resources for

a particular topic," (West & West 2009). However, there is one gap between these works, the absence of information in the perception of foreign language teachers on Wiki Technology in the classroom, while the whole works are directed at the perception of students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design to reveal the teachers' attitudes toward Wiki Technology in language learning. This questionnaire was conducted using a questionnaire. An online questionnaire was prepared using Google Forms and distributed through social media using a snowball technique among teaching staff, and administrative staff from Almaty, Kazakhstan. The questionnaire was originally made in English.

There are numerous Wiki tools available from various suppliers. The main functions of Wiki Technology were presented to teachers, along with a video clip created by the instructor that explained how to use the capabilities for the tasks.

Participants

This study involved 15 teachers of English departments at secondary schools from 3 schools as the research participants in Kazakhstan. Schools are located in Almaty: School №58; School №39, and School №202. All participants are English teachers who have well digital literacy, whereas an objective can be also suited for those who are new to the world of teaching

Instrument

The author utilized a questionnaire to collect the data written in the English language. Questions 1-7: General knowledge about basic digital technologies and Wikis, and how they are coping with them. Also, there were 10 items concerning the teachers' attitudes towards English language teaching which were divided into two parts: part 1 concentrated on the collaborative method of language teaching (5 items), and part 2 identified individual method of language teaching (5 items). The questionnaire was in the form of a Likert scale of 4 response options with strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), agree (3), and strongly agree (4) for parts. The Cronbach's alpha of the questionnaire was found to be

1.04. This meant that all questionnaire items were reliable to be used as a research instrument without any item deletion.

Research Procedure

The researchers created the questionnaire, analyzed the relevant literature, and evaluated the reliability of the instrument before conducting the study. The targeted respondents received the questionnaire after it satisfied the requirements. Additionally, emphasized was indeed the absolute secrecy of all information provided. After that, data analysis was carried out by first ensuring that the data were reliable. In order to provide a thorough pedagogical application, an investigation of crucial elements that influenced teachers' attitudes about English language instruction via Wiki technology was also examined.

Results

Sub-question 1.

A total of 15 language teachers at secondary school responded to the online questionnaire (100% response rate). All of the participants were females. As participants are teachers who have well digital literacy, and those who are new to the world of teaching, all 15 respondents use digital technologies in their teaching process (53.3% of teachers use it in the classroom, 40% of them for additional tasks, while 6.7% of them for home assignments). Among them, 53.03% of teachers choose Wiki technology as their favorite digital technology. The result of digital technologies' usage in their language classes was given in the next question (Figure 1). Before conducting a questionnaire these 15 teachers were informed about Wiki technology: its functions, essence, usage, advantages/ disadvantages and etc. Based on it we found that 4 (26.7%) teachers have an experience with the usage of Wiki Technology, whereas 66.7% of teachers know that technology well, but do not know how to use it. 10 teachers out of 15 teachers chose Wiki technology as suitable to complete the main topics of the course, based on it, of course, Wiki technology was chosen as "an effective way of teaching is using Wiki technology in FLE by teachers". According to the results, we can answer the question "Is it effective to use Wiki Technology for teachers in FLE?" as a lot of teachers (73.3%) also choose the following technology as suitable for activities such as collaborative, individual, and pair work.

Figure 1. Using different digital technologies in your classroom

Sub-question 2

Five questions concentrated on the collaborative method of language teaching and 5 questions identified individual methods of language teaching via a four-

point Likert scale (Table 1) The Cronbach's alpha of the questionnaire was found to be 1.04 which is a high acceptable level of reliability.

For the second sub-question, the following results can be evidence of it. 60% of teachers agree that Wiki technology helps teachers to provide an open space for students to freely express their individual views, 53.3% of them think that Wikis can be used by teachers as e-portfolios, a tool for collection and reflection at any time, from anywhere for each student, while 2 teachers disagree that Wikis helps teachers with versioning capability that can show the evolution of thought processes as student interacts with the site and its contents, others do not follow them. 9 teachers think that Wiki technology can serve teachers as a knowledge repository that can support reflection on the previous learning of each student, other 5 of them strongly agree. The same results have been shown for the next statement:

Online self-assessment surveys or quizzes via Wiki can be set up by teachers. After students' responses, teachers can easily add comments.

Sub-question 3

For individual methods of language teaching, 6 teachers hold an opinion that Wiki really can help teachers to integrate ideas and allow students to collaboratively share their thoughts and consider various possibilities, and other 8 teachers strongly agree with them. And other results from table 1 we can take as answers for the 3rd sub-question because here given the statements regarding that Wiki technology enables students to collaborative work that can establish students' social learning communities for knowledge creation and information sharing.

Table 1.

Likert scale to reveal the teachers' attitudes towards Wiki Technology in language learning									
Questions	1		2		3		4		Mode
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Part 1 identified individual methods of language teaching (5 items)									
1. Wiki technology helps teachers to provide an open space for students to freely express their individual views			1	6.7%	9	60%	5	33.3%	3
2. Wikis can be used by teachers as e-portfolios, a tool for collection and reflection at any time, from anywhere for each student					8	53.3%	7	46.7%	3
3. Wikis helps teachers with versioning capability that can show the evolution of thought processes as student interacts with the site and its contents			2	13.3%	8	53.3%	5	33.3%	3
4. Wiki technology can serve teachers as a knowledge repository that can support reflection on previous learning of each student			1	6.7%	9	60%	5	33.3%	3
5. Online self-assessment surveys or quizzes via Wiki can be set up by teachers. After students' responses, teachers can easily add comment			1	6.7%	9	60%	5	33.3%	3
Part 2 concentrated on the collaborative method of language teaching (5 items)									
1. Wiki really can help teachers to integrate ideas and allow students to collaboratively share their thoughts and consider various possibilities			1	6.7%	6	40%	8	53.3%	4
2. Students choose to use the wiki and ask their peers questions			2	13.3%	10	66.7%	3	20%	3
3. Wikis enable students to collaborative content creation, peer assessment; group reflection on learning experiences, and user-centric up-to-date information regarding changes in collaborative spaces which all facilitate knowledge sharing and group collaboration					9	60%	6	40%	3
4. Teacher monitors that collaborative projects enabled by Wikis can promote "pride of authorship" and ownership in the team's activities			1	6.7%	10	66.7%	4	26.7%	3
5. Online polling tools can be integrated with Wikis to support surveys and assessments by the teacher			2	13.3%	8	53.3%	5	33.3%	3

Discussion

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the perception of foreign language teachers on Wiki Technology in the classroom. The results of the study provided information about the efficiency of using Wiki Technology for teachers in FLE. Starting with the result, which was expected, Wiki was chosen as the

favorite technology among 15 participants. Actually, the popularity of wikis has begun to capture the attention of researchers and teachers in second/foreign language teaching, especially in second language writing already in more than 15 years ago. In the computer-mediated communication (CMC) contexts, writing is moving in the direction of "a more social construction of the

activity and interactivity of writing” (Pennington, 2003, p. 304). It should be noted that fifteen teachers, who participated in the research, were briefed about Wiki technology's functions, essence, usage, benefits, and drawbacks before completing a questionnaire. Since the majority of teachers have chosen Wiki technology as their favorite digital technology, the findings of the research did not all teachers have a good experience using it. Based on the seventh general question for all kinds of activities Wiki technology can be effective. This was similar to the findings of another study conducted by Purdy (2009) a wiki, as an asynchronous communication tool, supports many tenets of composition that are valued, including collaboration and pair work, continual revision, and communal knowledge formation.

According to the results from the 7th question from the Likert scale teachers agree that Wikis enable students to collaborate on content creation, peer assessment; group reflection on learning experiences, and user-centric up-to-date information regarding changes in collaborative spaces which all facilitate knowledge sharing and group collaboration. This was expected, the percentage of the choice 'agree' is high because all wiki applications have three functioning tabs: “Edit”, “History”, and “Discuss”. Based on the research Lund, our result can be justified that “Edit” allows the users to change or revise the page regarding the texts, images, or hyperlinks; “History” reflects the changes the page has gone through with the color coding of deleted and inserted texts; and “Discuss” enables the users to collaborate through messages about the page contents and revisions. Through features like user edit ability and detailed page history, wikis serve as powerful mediating artifacts for collaboration and support for collective production (Lund, 2008). According to the pre-last question result, participants agree with this the given statement: Teacher monitors that collaborative projects enabled by Wikis can promote “pride of authorship” and ownership in the team’s activities. Traditionally, the roles of instructor (expert) and student (novice) and the knowledge transfer process (from expert to novice) are clearly described. The traditional expert-novice relationship might change if an alternate knowledge-building mechanism, such as a wiki, is used (Ruth & Houghton 2009). Wiki technology has the ability to flatten traditional educational hierarchies, giving students greater autonomy and enticing them to exchange knowledge and educate one another (Ruth & Houghton 2009). Expertise is obtained by participation in the knowledge creation activity as opposed to possessing a substantial amount of prior information. Wikis may have the power to dismantle traditional social structures because the "expert" may no longer be the person with the most knowledge. The dynamics of wiki-mediated small-group interaction and the effects of these interactional patterns on students' real learning need to be further investigated. In addition, research on interaction during wiki-mediated writing activities has largely focused on student interactions, whereas studies examining student-teacher interactions are very rare. This might be due to the research designs where teachers served as observers or moderators rather than taking

part in the wiki project themselves. Thus, it can be deduced, a further research study can introduce the teacher’s active role in wiki-based writing activity, and explore how the teacher can scaffold students’ learning in the wiki environment.

Conclusion

The study gives teachers a general understanding of the effectiveness of wiki technology in foreign language education. Wiki technology has the ability to flatten traditional educational hierarchies, giving students greater autonomy and enticing them to exchange knowledge and educate one another, based on the results from the questionnaire, Wiki really can help teachers to integrate ideas and allow students to collaboratively share their thoughts and consider various possibilities. Wikis can be used to establish students' social learning communities for knowledge creation and information sharing, specifically wikis enable students to share information and to engage in/scaffold each other’s learning through student-to-student decision-making opportunities in group projects. Studying the perception of Wiki Technology for foreign language teachers in the classroom it can be concluded that it is really effective to use Wiki Technology for teachers in FLE.

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IMPLEMENTING CONSTRUCTIVIST PEDAGOGY IN ELT CLASSROOM

Manukyan A.

*PhD, Associate Professor at the Armenian State Pedagogical University
Yerevan, Armenia*

Abstract

The article considers Constructivist pedagogy implementation in the Armenian secondary schools. It investigates the results of practicing Constructivist theory in ELT classrooms. We examined how learners form their own representations of the world and receive new information based on their prior background knowledge as they experience and reflect on it. Thus learning becomes engaging and cooperative. The article considers the principles of constructive teaching, as well as it derives the differences between traditional classroom and constructivist classroom. It also introduces interactive implications for the ELT classroom by engaging students with real-life applications of how to use a tool instead of simply giving a list of prescribed instructions.

Keywords: Constructivist pedagogy, Constructivist learning theory, collaborative learning, constructivist teaching methods, principles and strategies of constructivist teaching.

*“Each time one prematurely teaches a child something
he could have discovered himself,
that child is kept from inventing it and
consequently, from understanding it completely.”
Jean Piaget*

Constructivism is a philosophy of learning founded on the premise that, by reflecting on our experiences, we construct our own understanding of the world we live in. Each of us generates our own “rules and mental models”, which we use to make sense of our experiences.

Constructivism as a learning theory/ A brief history

Constructivism as a theory which is defined as a learning process when the learners construct knowledge rather than just passively input the information provided. As people experience the world and reflect upon those experiences, they build their own representations and incorporate new information into

their pre-existing knowledge (schemas). The teacher who implements constructivism at classes they believe that in order to learn, students need as many hands-on experiences with objects, skills, and people as possible. Constructivism provides students with rich experiences and encourages them to draw their own conclusions.

Jean Piaget is considered the founder of the constructivist view of learning. As a biologist, he was interested in how an organism adapts to the environment and how previous mental knowledge contributes to behaviors. Knowledge is not a snapshot of reality; in order to understand something, you don't just simply look at it and make a mental copy of it. In order to truly recognize the environment, we must act on it. According to